

CHARACTERIZATION OF RESIN FLOW THROUGH THICK LAMINATES IN RESIN TRANSFER MOULDING

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ABSTRACT

This paper addresses the problems of fluid flow characterization during impregnation of thick laminates. It introduces a novel method to measure the permeabilities in three dimensions of orthotropic fibre mats. This method is an extension of the widely used radial flow test. By introducing thermistors it is possible to measure spatial variations of fluid flow. A closed form solution of Darcy's law in spherical coordinates is also developed to obtain permeability values.

1. INTRODUCTION

Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) is increasingly used for low to medium volume production of high quality laminates. Whereas much of the previous work has focused on the production of thin laminates, increasing interest of applying RTM to shipbuilding implies a need to study thick laminates. One approach to understand resin impregnation is through two- and three-dimensional flow simulation. There are at least two different approaches to three-dimensional flow modelling in RTM. Firstly the three-dimensional flow is transformed into an equivalent two-dimensional problem by developing an analytical expression to model transverse flow effects at the flow front for thin-shell geometries [1]. The second, more widely used approach employs a full three-dimensional analysis applying Darcy's law and the continuity equation to control volume/finite element programmes [2]. However all studies lack an experimental verification of the mould filling process within the mould cavity apart from inlet pressure and flow front at the mould surface.

To obtain the necessary material data for these flow simulation programmes, tests to determine permeability are carried out. There are two different one-dimensional flow configurations - channel flow and radial flow. The former yields the permeability for steady state flow in a saturated porous medium. The latter [3] measures the unsaturated flow of the fluid by recording the position of the flow front and time passed. It is probably the more realistic flow measurement approach for the RTM process. The aim of this paper is to introduce a novel three-dimensional flow measurement technique which is based on the radial flow test.

2. DESCRIBING FLOW BEHAVIOUR

Governing equation

The flow through porous media is described by Darcy's law:

$$u = - \frac{K_x}{\mu} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} \quad (1)$$

where u is the mean velocity in x -direction, P the pressure, μ the viscosity and K_x the permeability in x -direction. Substituting Darcy's law for the velocities in the continuity equation yields:

$$K_x \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial x^2} + K_y \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial y^2} + K_z \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (2)$$

For an isotropic material $K_x = K_y = K_z = K$. The pressure and velocity distributions are obtained by solving the Laplace equation. In the case of an orthotropic material i.e. with one plane of symmetry, Laplace's equation has to be transformed into a quasi-isotropic equation which will be discussed in the next section.

Permeability measurement

In this investigation, only isothermal flow of a Newtonian fluid is considered. The viscosity μ therefore remains constant throughout the simulation. To determine the spatial variation of permeability requires measurements in the through-thickness direction of either pressure variation or velocity variation. Simple calculations have shown that dynamic pressure variations are on a mPa scale and very difficult to detect. The static pressure shows also minimal variation in through thickness direction. The other option therefore is to measure velocity. Commonly used techniques like observing flow front progression are unsuitable for detecting spatial variations of flow front. Thermistors seem to be a good solution to this problem [4]. They are available in very small sizes and produce distinctly different signals under heat and when cooled by the advancing flow front due to the high negative temperature coefficient of the resistance.

3. RADIAL FLOW TEST AND ORTHOTROPY

Two-dimensional radial flow

In the radial flow test the radius of the advancing flow front is measured as function of time. It is unsaturated flow since the flow front is advancing through dry fibres. The fluid is usually injected at constant pressure. A closed form solution for the isotropic permeability has been derived from the continuity equation and Darcy's law [5]. The task of determining the permeability becomes more difficult when the fabric or mat is orthotropic. The most common approach is to transform the system into a quasi-isotropic system by scaling the x and y coordinates as below:

$$K' = \sqrt{K_x K_y} ; \quad \bar{x} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{K_y}{K_x}} x ; \quad \bar{y} = \sqrt[4]{\frac{K_x}{K_y}} y ; \quad R = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2} \quad (3)$$

$$K' \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \bar{x}^2} + K' \frac{\partial^2 P}{\partial \bar{y}^2} = 0 \quad (4)$$

The resulting equation is Laplace's equation with permeability K' . By solving this equation for pressure and combining it with Darcy's law, a solution for the quasi-isotropic permeability is obtained:

$$K' = (R_f^2 [2 \ln\{R_f / R_o\} - 1] + R_o^2) \frac{\mu \epsilon}{4t \Delta P} \quad (5)$$

where R_f is flow front radius, R_o the radius of inlet, ϵ the porosity, t is the time to reach R_f and ΔP is the pressure difference between inlet and flow front. The orthotropic permeability of flow in the x -direction, for instance, is obtained by substituting for R and K' as defined above at $y=0$:

$$K_x = (x_f^2 [2 \ln\{x_f / x_o\} - 1] + x_o^2) \frac{\mu \epsilon}{4t \Delta P} \quad (6)$$

where x_f is the flow front radius in x -direction and x_o is the inlet radius. The next step is to plot the flow front radii (term in round brackets) versus time t . A regression line is fitted through the data points to obtain the slope, K_x can then be determined from Eqn (6). K_y is obtained in a similar manner by setting $x = 0$.

Three-dimensional spherical flow

When injecting into a thick laminate from the bottom of a mould, flow occurs in an open, unrestricted space. The initial wetted domain has the shape of a hemi-sphere or in the orthotropic case of an ellipsoid. To obtain an analytical solution for this situation it is best to use spherical coordinates:

$$\nabla^2 P = \frac{d^2 P}{dr^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{dP}{dr} \quad (7)$$

with the following transformations:

$$K' = K_z ; \quad \bar{x} = \sqrt{\frac{K_z}{K_x}} x ; \quad \bar{y} = \sqrt{\frac{K_z}{K_y}} y ; \quad \bar{z} = z ; \quad R = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad (8)$$

A solution for quasi-isotropic permeability is then obtained:

$$K' = \frac{\mu \epsilon}{t \Delta P} \frac{R_f^3}{3R_o} \left(1 - \frac{3R_o}{2R_f} + \frac{R_o^3}{2R_f^3} \right) \quad (9)$$

The structure of this formula is different from that of the radial flow situation. This is because

radial flow takes place between two plates while there is no restriction in the spherical flow case. The orthotropic permeabilities are obtained in exactly the same way as described in the previous paragraph i.e. by substituting for R and K' and fitting a regression line to x_f or y_f or z_f versus t .

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Apparatus

The test rig is of modular design and is suitable for radial and channel flow tests [6]. It has an aluminum work surface with a supporting steel structure and maximum working section of 400 x 1300 mm. Data acquisition includes video recording facility as well as a PC to record and process inlet pressure transducer and thermistor readings.

Experiments

To validate the theory developed in the last section a number of tests have been conducted. These comprised a series of thin (4.6mm) radial injection tests where the flow front was recorded with a video camera and thick injections of 20-25mm thickness (35-43 plies) where thermistors were employed to record the flow front. All the test were done at constant pressure. The test fluid was a mineral oil (Shell Vitrea Oil, M100) with a viscosity of 330 mPa at 18°C. The continuous filament mat tested was the U750-450 from Vetrotex. The video recordings were played onto a Silicon Graphics work station to measure the flow front radius using AVS software.

Through-thickness flow front measurement

The flow front is detected by placing small thermistors (1.5mm diameter) at different locations through the depth and width of the mould lay-up. The thermistors are heated initially with a power input of about 20 mW each. This is enough to raise the surface temperature sufficiently to experience a large enough temperature and resistance change to give a distinct voltage jump when the fluid reaches the thermistor. A typical result for a thick laminate injection is shown in Figure 1. Each line represents the voltage reading over time of a single thermistor. Through tests it was discovered that the optimal lay-up for the thermistors and its wires is across the flow, rather than parallel to it. It appears that the wires form some kind of channel when in line with the flow and therefore advance the flow front more rapidly than in the neighbouring area. However this problem disappears once the wires are far enough apart.

5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Validation of Eqn (5)

The simplified solution of the Laplace equation for the radial flow test, Eqn (5), is in good agreement with the published examples by Adams *et al.* [5] and Chan and Hwang [7]. Permeability in the x-direction was calculated as being 5.34×10^{-10} . This compares with Chan's value of 5.38×10^{-10} . From Adams data a K_x value of 5.39×10^{-10} was calculated compared with Adam's 5.27×10^{-10} . Permeability in the y-direction is 3.67×10^{-10} compared with Chan's 4.01×10^{-10} and 3.74×10^{-10} compared with Adams's 3.90×10^{-10} . Because of the (assumed) orthotropic behaviour of the porous material, the analytical solution of permeability along one axis is independent of the other permeabilities. This simplifies the computational effort to fitting only

one regression line to obtain the average permeability in the direction of interest. In contrast to that, when using Chan's method it is necessary to fit two regression lines and in Adam's approach one regression line and an iterative solution is required.

Radial and spherical flow results

The results of the radial flow tests are summarised in Figure 2 and Figure 3. They show the permeability for different fibre volume fractions and injection pressures. It is interesting to note that the permeability is slightly lower when injecting at a higher pressure; for instance at a fibre volume fraction of 0.23, K_x is $1.58 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ at 118 kPa and $1.35 \times 10^{-9} \text{ m}^2$ at 233 kPa. Table 1 gives some results from injection tests into thick laminates. A small dependence on pressure is noticed here as well. As expected the through-thickness permeability K_z is lower than the in-plane permeabilities.

Discussion

To be able to compare the results of the two different test configurations, permeability has been plotted against the flow front radius normalised to thickness Figure 4. This time permeability calculated for each point of measurement has been plotted rather than an average value for a test. This is a good measure for convergence or "robustness" of the results. Applying Eqn (5) to the results of tests 5 to 8 shows good convergence behaviour. Even though there is a small gradient initially the permeability settles to a constant value. When the same equation is applied to experiment 9 the results are not as satisfactory and in experiment 11 there is apparently even an decrease for increasing flow front radius. Similar observation can be made with Eqn (9). For experiment 11 the numerical values are as expected even though convergence behaviour is not good in this case. If this equation is applied to experiment 9 the results becomes very unstable.

To explain this behaviour it is best to compare Eqns (5) and (9). Assuming the same viscosity, porosity, time and pressure difference the above mentioned equations can be combined to yield the following relationship:

$$\frac{1}{4} \left(R_{f-r}^2 [2 \ln(R_{f-r} / R_o) - 1] + R_o^2 \right) = \frac{R_{f-s}^3}{3 R_o} \left(1 - \frac{3R_o}{2R_{f-s}} + \frac{R_o^3}{2R_{f-s}^3} \right) \quad (10)$$

where R_{f-r} is the flow front radius for radial flow and R_{f-s} the flow front radius for the spherical case. By comparing right and left hand sides of this equation it becomes obvious that R_{f-s} has to be smaller than R_{f-r} . This explains the behaviour of the two governing equations. Eqn (5) showed a decrease in permeability with increasing flow front radius when applied in the "spherical" domain because of the apparently shorter radius. Applying Eqn (9) to the radial domain (Experiments 5-9) showed a very unstable behaviour with steep increases in permeability. This can be attributed to the fact that the observed flow front radii are too large for the spherical model.

Figure 5 is a plot of radial and spherical pressure distribution. A very steep pressure gradient can be observed for smaller radii values for the spherical case. Therefore a small disturbance of the pressure distribution changes the flow behaviour markedly. This helps to explain the unstable behaviour of experiment 11. For the through-thickness measurements, the opposite mould face was reached after 15 seconds. The horizontal in plane flow measurements were taken at slightly longer intervals though it was still a short term flow observation. A solution will be to increase the thickness to 40 to 45 mm and/or reduce the injection pressure from 150 kPa to 100 kPa. This would increase the filling time substantially and should improve

consistency of the permeability results.

In summarizing it can be said that the radial flow equation Eqn (5) works very well beyond length to thickness ratios of about 15-20. In contrast the spherical flow equation Eqn (9) is limited to the time until the flow front reaches the opposite face in the through-thickness direction. The limit of the horizontal radius is determined by the ratio of $\sqrt{(K_y/K_x)}$. For practical purposes the horizontal flow front radius should not exceed the product of thickness and $\sqrt{(K_y/K_x)}$ by more than 1.5. The results of experiment 9 represent a border case, where both of the equations do not work properly.

6. CONCLUSION

A novel permeability measurement technique for measuring permeability in three dimensions has been introduced. It is based on the well proven radial flow test. Thermistors have been successfully applied to obtain spatial variations of flow front progression. In the development process of the underlying theory some simplifications have been introduced to the analytical solution which are also beneficial to the two-dimensional radial flow test. Limits of the application of the two and three-dimensional permeability formula have been discussed. As already mentioned in the discussion more tests are required to improve the data base of the spherical case. These should include different fluids (reactive resins) and different types of fibre mat or fabric.

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FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 1 Voltage change of thermistors

Figure 2 Permeability - radial flow (K_x)

Figure 3 Permeability - radial flow (K_y)

Table 1 Permeability - spherical flow

test number	9	11	12
permeability values	$K_x = 1.42 \times 10^{-9}$ $K_y = 1.34 \times 10^{-9}$ $K_z = --$	$K_x = 5.11 \times 10^{-10}$ $K_y = 5.14 \times 10^{-10}$ $K_z = 9.56 \times 10^{-11}$	$K_x = 2.95 \times 10^{-10}$ $K_y = 4.41 \times 10^{-10}$ $K_z = 6.51 \times 10^{-11}$
test details	$P = 167 \text{ kPa}$ $h = 20.5 \text{ mm}$ $x_{\text{max}} = 156 \text{ mm}$ $t_{\text{max}} = 227 \text{ s}$ number of plies: 35	$P = 132 \text{ kPa}$ $h = 25.1 \text{ mm}$ $x_{\text{max}} = 72 \text{ mm}$ $t_{\text{max}} = 72.2 \text{ s}$ number of plies: 43	$P = 137 \text{ kPa}$ $h = 25.1 \text{ mm}$ $x_{\text{max}} = 36 \text{ mm}$ $t_{\text{max}} = 18.6 \text{ s}$ number of plies: 43

Figure 4 Permeability versus x over thickness (h)

Figure 5 Comparison of radial and spherical pressure distribution